

The insect populations in the other field were similar. But the level of WBPH was higher, about 10 WBPH/hill at 45 DT (see figure, B). That level is below the tentative economic threshold of 20/hill in the Muda Irrigation Scheme. Interestingly, only the two fields were untreated throughout the planting

season. The surrounding 29 fields had more than 20 WBPH/hill and were subsequently sprayed. All of the affected fields were prophylactically treated with carbofuran granules at 30 DT. Such observations highlight the need for an integrated pest control approach in Malaysia. ■

Pest occurrence on split transplanted rice

P. B. Chatterjee and M. Sarkar, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Pandua 712149, Hooghly, India

In West Bengal, split transplanting or clonal propagation of rice is practiced mostly in flood-prone areas where farmers generally face a shortage of seedlings after the floodwater recedes.

A preliminary investigation conducted at Pandua, a gall-midge endemic area, studied the effect of split transplanting on pest incidence in wetland rice. Thirty-day-old seedlings of

Pankaj, an aman rice, were transplanted in the main field (T_1). The rooting tillers of Pankaj were split and transplanted in another field 20 days later (T_2). Subsequently two other fields were transplanted with 40- and 60-day-old tillers (T_3 and T_4), split from the first transplanted field. The spacing was 20×15 cm; 3 seedlings/hill were transplanted. The fertilizer dose was 75-25-25 kg NPK/ha. The field was 100 m^2 and the water level was maintained at 5-7 cm during the vegetative stage. No pesticide was applied. Split transplanting of seedlings 20 days after the first transplanting was the best treatment (see table). ■

Effect of split transplanting on blast disease incidence and gall midge infestation. Hooghly, India.

Split-transplant treatment	Tillers (no./m ²)	Blast infection in leaves (%)	Silver shoots (no./m ²)	Earhead lengths (cm)	Fertile grains/earhead ^a (no.)	Yield/100 m ²
T_1 (control)	373	5	32	23.3	96.65	5.4
T_2 (20-day)	360	1	9	22.3	106.0	5.6
T_3 (40-day)	164	1	5	8.4	80.6	3.8
T_4 (60-day)	119	1	5	8.1	72.0	3.0

^aMean of 20 earheads.

Rice insects and their management in the Ord river irrigation area of Western Australia

S. E. Learmonth, entomologist, Department of Agriculture, Kununurra, Western Australia 6743

Both a wet and a dry season crop of rice are grown on the Ord, where rice production is still being developed. Rice is grown on about 400 ha each season. The rice pest complex in the two seasons differs; infestations are more severe in the wet season crops.

The rice white stem borer *Tryporyza innotata* is the most consistent and the most damaging insect in the wet

season. Its natural control agents are being studied; the major ones are the egg parasite *Telenomus rowani* (see table) and the late larval parasite *Temelucha* sp., which cause roughly 40% parasitism over the season. *Bracon* sp., a parasite of early larval instars, is found, but usually in low abundance.

Other research is conducted on insecticide screening and time-of-application trials. seasonal abundance of moths for predictive insecticide application in commercial crops (granular lindane is used), and plant varietal resistance to stem borers. The army-worm *Pseudaletia separata*, a serious rice pest in the panicle development-maturity

Egg parasitism of *Tryporyza innotata* (98% by *Telenomus rowani*). The wet season experimental crops are sown early in December. Ord River, Australia, 1978-79.

Date	Eggs (no.)	Parasitism (%)
10 Jan 1978	5141	43
20 Jan	1628	57
25 Jan	600	94
13 Feb	991	61
22 Feb	1239	57
2 Mar	1561	80
27 Dec 1978	353	0
4 Jan 1979	447	0
10 Jan	643	0
1 Feb	438	15
7 Feb	1248	31
12 Feb	2782	20
15 Feb	836	36
22 Feb	3014	71
2 Mar	1051	55
14 Mar	1648	67
23 Mar	214	80
29 Mar	776	55
11 Apr	1485	71

stage, causes grain to fall. Other pests include the grain-sucking bug *Eysarcoris trimaculatus* and locusts (chiefly *Gastrimargus musicus*, *Locusta migratoria*, and *Austracris guttulosa*).

Dry season rice crops are attacked by *P. separata* and *E. trimaculatus*, but not as severely as the wet season crops. Rice bloodworms Chironomidae occasionally attack aerially sown, dry season crops.

Leafhoppers are found in Ord rice crops but so far have not caused damage nor transmitted serious diseases. ■

Influence of nitrogen levels on rice hispa incidence

G. S. Dhaliwal, H. N. Shahi, P. S. Gill, and M. S. Maskina, Punjab Agricultural University, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala 144601, India

In a field trial during 1978 kharif, the infestation by rice hispa *Didaspis armigera* increased with an increase in nitrogen level from 0 to 120 kg/ha. At 150 kg N/ha, however, infestation decreased considerably. The mean numbers of hispa-damaged leaves/10 hills at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha were 67, 90, 115, 145, 171, and 128, respectively.

The decrease in rice hispa incidence

at the highest nitrogen level of 150 kg/ha might have been due to some deleterious effect of excessive nitrogen on the

feeding activity of the insect. Alternatively, it might also have been due to the plants' more bushy growth, which left

few leaf tips exposed for egg-laying. Rice hispa prefers widely spaced exposed leaves to partly hidden leaf tips. ■

Brown planthopper outbreaks and associated yield losses in Malaysia

G. S. Lim, Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (MARDI), Serdang, Selangor; A.C.P. Ooi, Department of Agriculture, Telok Chengai, Kedah; and A.K. Koh, Drainage and Irrigation Department, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

The effects of brown planthopper (BPH) outbreaks on plant growth and yield are complex and variable; they are largely governed by the time and duration of attack, intensity of injury, and environmental factors that affect both insect activities and plant growth. Attempts are frequently made to estimate yield losses to determine the actual

importance of the pest.

One common method is to compare the yields of infested and pest-free crops. In a yield loss assessment during the 1977 BPH outbreak in Tanjong Karang, Malaysia, yields of 10.1- × 10.1-m plots were taken. For each locality from 6 to 15 plots were analyzed. The plots constituted fixed sample areas, randomly selected for the national crop-cutting survey. The yield reduction for the infested crops was measured against the yields for uninfested crops similarly sampled during a few earlier seasons.

In Tanjong Karang, the BPH outbreak was initially detected on 13 June in Sekinchan, where 20–30 BPH/hill were recorded (see map). From there the damage rapidly spread to surrounding

areas. On 8 July from 500 to 1,000 BPH/hill were found on plants in Sungai Burong. Soon more than 405 ha were affected (about 28 ha were severely hopperburned), and the outbreak spread to other areas.

Although the BPH spread almost throughout the rice-growing areas in Tanjong Karang during the 1977 outbreak, crop damage was limited to a few localities (see map). Only 1,620 ha of the total 20,243 ha of double-cropped land were ultimately destroyed by hopperburn.

Yield losses were generally severe in all localities where BPH infestation and hopperburn were high. For example, in Sungai Burong, Sungai Leman, and Sungai Pasir Panjang, the severely

Tanjong Karang Irrigation Scheme.